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Research Article

PREVALENCE OF BURNOUT SYNDROME AMONG MEDICAL RESIDENTS OF VARIOUS SPECIALTIES IN MAKKAH

Sajeed Nazirudheen¹, Alharbi Rahaf², Alharbi Raghad², Thiga Ghaliyah²,
Alsharif Mohammed³

¹RN., MSc. N Coronary Care Unit, King Abdullah Medical City, Makkah

²Medical Intern at Umm alQura University – Makkah

³Medical Intern King Khalid University - Abha

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Abstract:

Background: Burnout syndrome is defined by the World Health Organization as “a result from chronic workplace stress that has not been successfully managed”. It is characterized according to MBI (Maslach burnout inventory) by three dimensions: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and personal accomplishment. **Objectives:** We aim to determine the prevalence of burnout syndrome among medical residents of various specialties in Makkah in addition to measuring its association with sociodemographic characteristics of the sample. We also aim to compare the prevalence of burnout among different specialties. **Methods:** This was a cross-sectional study conducted on 181 residents in Makkah using a valid questionnaire composed of two parts: the first part includes questions about the personal and professional characteristics of Medical residents. The second part includes the Maslach burnout inventory (MBI) English version (5), there are three components in the questionnaire: burnout, depersonalization, and personal achievement. It was distributed by Co-investigators and completed by medical residents. **Results:** In the assessment of the three burnout domains (Burnout, Depersonalization, and personal achievements), High-level burnout was found among 38.1%, 75.1%, and 48.1% of the residents in the three domains respectively. Burnout score mean was 25±9.4, Depersonalization score mean was 20.2±10.4, and Personal achievements score mean was 34±8.7. No significant association was found between gender and any of the domains. However, a significant association was found between specialty and burnout domain. **Conclusion:** Our study supports previous results in the prevalence of burnout among residents, most common among neurology residents. These findings highly recommend serious strategies to be implemented to lessen the burden among residents.

Corresponding author:

Sajeed Nazirudheen,

RN., MSc. N Coronary Care Unit,

King Abdullah Medical City, Makkah

QR code

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I. BACKGROUND:

Burnout syndrome is defined by the World Health Organization as the condition that results from chronic workplace stress that has not been successfully managed. It is characterized by three dimensions: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and personal accomplishment. (1)

Health care workers reported to be vulnerable to burnout syndrome with prevalence found for all medical specialties was 35.7% This prevalence varied according to specialties; with the high rate among General Surgery, Obstetrics/Gynecology 40.8% followed by Internal Medicine and Pediatrics 30.0% while Otolaryngology and Neurology reported lower rate 15.4%. (2)

Burnout was associated with several factors including; age, sex, marital status, and nationality. (12,13,14,15) Several studies associate vulnerability to burnout with age; they reported higher levels of burnout among younger doctors. (6, 7, 8, 9) It was also reported in two papers a significant association between female gender and Emotional Exhaustion (EE)/burnout (10,11)

Burnout is a significant predictor of the following physical consequences: musculoskeletal pain, prolonged fatigue, headaches, and gastrointestinal issues. Psychological effects were reported to be insomnia, depressive symptoms, use of psychotropic and antidepressant medications. (3)

The researchers in their clinical experience found that the residents were more exposed to burnout during their working hours. The researchers also noted that the Burnout syndrome is a very serious and common problem. It is increasing rapidly among medical residents, and it has a negative effect on physicians' health, patients' health and their satisfaction, family members and friends, the world economy, and patient safety. (2, 4)

The prevalence of burnout among healthcare professionals can be attributed to several external factors including; loss of autonomy, too many bureaucratic tasks, spending too many hours at work, and increased demand for using electronic health records (EHRs). (16,17)

In an attempt to reduce and prevent burnout, both individual-focused and organizational strategies have been found to bring clinically meaningful reductions in burnout among physicians. However, there is not enough data to decide whether a particular approach

is more suitable for a specific population. (18) To name a few of previously suggested approaches we mention: leadership involvement in the issue of burnout, Better choices of incentives which suggests usage of performance-independent salary models or other alternative rewards, work-life balance encouragement, Peer-support application, Providing more resources for self-care and mental health, and targeting burnout issue since day one of medical school. (16)

Saudi Arabia in turn had its share of burnout. A cross-sectional study was conducted in two major tertiary hospitals in Makkah, Saudi Arabia showed that the prevalence of burnout among health care workers in ICU was found to be frequent in Hajj time, with the highest level of severe burnout in the post-cardiac surgery ICU 32% followed by the main ICU 22.2%. (Dr. Tharwat Aisa 2018, personal communication)

In another cross-sectional study conducted in a tertiary hospital, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia on 348 participants, 46% of whom were residents, the prevalence of burnout was found to be 70%. (8)

II. Objectives:**Primary Objective:**

To determine the prevalence of burnout syndrome among medical residents of various specialties in Makkah.

Secondary Objective:

- To compare the determinants of the syndrome in groups of participants with the various socio-demographic data among medical residents of various specialties at Makkah.
- To Compare Burnout Syndrome among different Specialties.
- To Compare Burnout Syndrome among different health Centers.
- To determine the adverse impacts of medical residents' burnout from the Maslach burnout inventory (MBI) questionnaire.

II. Study design:

Descriptive/Analytical Cross-sectional study.

III. Study Population:

All medical residents from various specialties (General surgery, obstetrics/gynecology, Internal medicine, Oncology, Neurology, Pediatrics, ICU, Otolaryngology) in Makkah.

Selection criteria:

Inclusion criteria:

- All medical residents from various specialties in Makkah.
- Medical residents who want to participate in the study.

Exclusion criteria:

- Refusal of the Research by the participants.
- Medical residents who are already diagnosed with any mental health illness before joining the residency program.

IV. Study procedures:

Data that has main sections were collected using a validated questionnaire. The first part includes questions about the personal and professional characteristics of Medical residents. The second part includes the Maslach burnout inventory (MBI) English version (5), there are three components in the questionnaire: burnout, depersonalization, and personal achievement. It was distributed by Co-investigators and completed by medical residents. The study took place in a period of 2 weeks for data collection.

V. Sample size determination

Assumed	Confidence limit	Confidence level	Number needed
30%	4%	95%	2065
30%	6%	95%	928
35%	6%	95%	1003
35%	8%	95%	569
40%	8%	95%	599
40%	6%	95%	1056

At a confidence level of 95% and an Assumed percentage of 35% (including low, moderate, and high burnout) with a confidence limit of 8% our sample size will be 569. An in term analysis was carried out by the end of the student summer program and the data collection was continued for one year after the program.

VI. Statistical Analysis Plan:

Statistical Package for Social Sciences software, version 26 was used for all statistical analyses. Comparison between groups (BO versus no BO) were made by Pearson's Chi-Square test for categorical values and for the occurrence of BO among different specialties and by other grouping variables. Alpha was two-tailed and was set at 0.05

Outcome Assessment:

Percentage of each degree of burnout syndrome among medical residents of various specialties in Makkah. The scoring will be as follows:

- Burnout: low burnout ≤ 17 , moderate burnout from 18 to 29, high burnout ≥ 30 .
- Depersonalization: low depersonalization ≤ 5 , moderate depersonalization from 6 to 11, high depersonalization ≥ 12 .
- Personal achievement: high-level burnout ≤ 33 , moderate burnout from 34 to 39, and low-level burnout ≥ 40 .

VI. Data collection and management:

Data were collected from medical residents by Survey Monkey website, and it was collected by participant or researcher, their E-mails were taken from academic affairs at KAMC after IRB approval for the lists of residents' names, contacted them and sent them the survey by E-mail, in addition, we sent a reminder to those who did not respond. Five different persons performed data entry. After verification, data was transferred to the statistical database directly.

for all comparisons.

VII. Ethical part & confidentiality:

Ethical approval was obtained from KAMC IRB. Data was carefully handled and confidentiality was maintained throughout the entire process of data management.

VIII. RESULTS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted on 181 participants of residents from different specialties in Makkah; 53% of whom were females and 47% males. Equal percentages were found in the married and single population (48.6% each), with only 2.8% divorced. The majority were found to be Saudi

(98.3%), with only 35.9% of smokers. It was also noted that none of them suffered from any mental illness formerly. (Table 1)

The data included residents from different specialties with the majority coming from Internal Medicine (22.7%), followed by General Surgery (16%) and Obstetrics/Gynecology (14.4%). The highest percentage of residents came from King Abdullah Medical City (28.7%) and Al Noor Specialist Hospital (22.1%). The majority of participants were in their R1-R3 years of residency (31.5%, 26.0%, 23.8% respectively), also 89% had On-call duties with more than half of them have them 6-9 times per month. (Table 2)

The assessment of the three burnout domains (Burnout, Depersonalization, and personal achievements) revealed high-level burnout was found among 38.1%, 75.1%, and 48.1% of the residents in the three domains respectively. Burnout score mean was 25 ± 9.4 , Depersonalization score mean was 20.2 ± 10.4 , and Personal achievements score mean was 34 ± 8.7 . (Table 3, 4, 5, 6)

No association was found between Burnout levels in different domains and socio-demographic factors including sex, marital status, nationality, and smoking. (Table 7) However, a significant association was found between burnout level and specialty (P-Value = 0.020), and between residency level and personal achievements (P-Value = 0.049)

Table (1): Description of Socio-demographic characteristics of the participants (N=181)

Parameter	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
Male	85	47.0%
Female	96	53.0%
Marital status		
Single	88	48.6%
Married	88	48.6%
Divorced	5	2.8%
Nationality		
Saudi	178	98.3%
Non-Saudi	3	1.7%
Current smoker		
Yes	65	35.9%
No	116	64.1%
History of mental illnesses		
No	181	100.0%

Table (2): Work-related data of the participants (N=181)

Parameter	Frequency	Percent
Specialty		
General Surgery	29	16.0%
Obstetrics/Gynecology	26	14.4%
Internal Medicine	41	22.7%
Oncology	7	3.9%
Neurology	7	3.9%
Pediatrics	23	12.7%
ICU	14	7.7%
Otolaryngology	10	5.5%
Emergency Medicine	24	13.3%
Hospital of work		
King Abdullah Medical City	52	28.7%
Maternity and children's hospital	22	12.2%
Al Noor Specialist Hospital	40	22.1%
King Faisal Hospital	19	10.5%
Hera General Hospital	29	16.0%
Security forces Hospital	19	10.5%
Year of residency		
R1	57	31.5%
R2	47	26.0%
R3	43	23.8%
R4	25	13.8%
R5	9	5.0%
On-call duties		
Yes	161	89.0%
No	20	11.0%
If yes, how many times per month? (N=161)		
Less than 5 times	40	24.8%
6-9 times	93	57.8%
More than 9 times	28	17.4%

Table (3): Burnout domain responses among participants (N=181)

Parameter	Never	A few times a year	Once a month	Few times a month	Once a week	A few times a week	Daily
I feel emotionally drained by my Work	1.7%	7.2%	9.4%	27.1%	7.7%	27.6%	19.3%
Working with people all day long requires a great deal of effort	2.8%	4.4%	7.2%	13.8%	14.9%	26.0%	30.9%
I feel like my work is breaking me down	7.7%	13.3%	12.7%	17.1%	15.5%	21.5%	12.2%
I feel frustrated by my work	5.5%	17.1%	11.6%	18.2%	11.6%	30.4%	5.5%
I feel I work too hard at my job	1.7%	3.9%	8.8%	18.2%	11.0%	30.9%	25.4%
It stresses me too much to work in direct contact with people	13.3%	8.3%	11.6%	18.8%	13.3%	18.2%	16.6%
I feel like I'm at the end of my rope	19.3%	13.8%	13.8%	22.1%	10.5%	13.3%	7.2%
Burnout score (Mean±SD)	25±9.4						

Table (4): Depersonalization domain responses among participants (N=181)

Parameter	Never	A few times a year	Once a month	Few times a month	Once a week	A few times a week	Daily
I feel I look after certain patients/clients impersonally, as if they are objects	19.3%	14.4%	13.3%	18.2%	16.0%	13.3%	5.5%
I feel tired when I get up in the morning and have to face another day at work	3.3%	11.0%	13.3%	24.9%	13.3%	19.3%	14.9%
I have the impression that my patients/clients make me responsible for some of their problems	11.0%	8.8%	7.7%	23.8%	10.5%	27.6%	10.5%
I am at the end of my patience at the end of my workday	6.6%	13.3%	12.2%	20.4%	8.8%	24.3%	14.4%
I really don't care about what happens to some of my patients/clients	37.6%	14.4%	17.1%	16.0%	6.1%	6.6%	2.2%
I have become more insensitive to people since I've been working	17.7%	15.5%	7.2%	16.6%	12.2%	22.1%	8.8%
I'm afraid that this job is making me uncaring	23.2%	16.0%	7.2%	12.2%	9.9%	22.1%	9.4%
Depersonalization score (Mean±SD)	20.2±10.4						

Table (5): Personal achievement domain responses among participants (N=181)

Parameter	Never	A few times a year	Once a month	Few times a month	Once a week	A few times a week	Daily
I accomplish many worthwhile things in this job	2.8%	9.4%	8.3%	19.9%	11.6%	24.3%	23.8%
I feel full of energy	5.0%	6.6%	10.5%	28.7%	16.0%	22.7%	10.5%
I am easily able to understand what my patients/clients feel	2.2%	5.0%	6.1%	13.3%	18.2%	32.0%	23.2%
I look after my patients & clients problems very effectively	1.1%	1.1%	4.4%	13.3%	17.1%	32.6%	30.4%
In my work, I handle emotional problems very calmly	1.7%	2.8%	9.4%	16.0%	13.3%	35.9%	21.0%
Through my work, I feel that I have a positive influence on people	2.2%	5.0%	9.4%	19.3%	13.3%	26.5%	24.3%
I am easily able to create a relaxed atmosphere with my patients/clients	1.7%	6.6%	6.6%	16.6%	17.1%	27.6%	23.8%
I feel refreshed when I have been close to my patients/clients at work	3.9%	7.7%	14.9%	16.0%	15.5%	21.5%	20.4%
Personal achievement score (Mean±SD)	34±8.7						

Table (6): Burnout domains categories based on scores (N=181)

Parameter	Burnout	Depersonalization	Personal achievement
Low level burnout	23.8%	7.7%	22.7%
Moderate burnout	38.1%	17.1%	29.3%
High-level burnout	38.1%	75.1%	48.1%
Total	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
High-level burnout in at least one domain	79.0%		
High-level burnout in all domains	26.0%		

Table (7): Burnout levels in different domains in association with socio-demographic factors (N=181)

Parameter		Burnout level		P-value	Depersonalization level		P-value	Personal achievement		P-value
		Low burnout	High burnout		Low burnout	High burnout		Low burnout	High burnout	
Sex	Male	63.5%	36.5%	0.667	29.4%	70.6%	0.187	47.1%	52.9%	0.217
	Female	60.4%	39.6%		20.8%	79.2%		56.3%	43.8%	
Marital status	Single	58.0%	42.0%	0.453	23.9%	76.1%	0.911	54.5%	45.5%	0.265
	Married	64.8%	35.2%		26.1%	73.9%		51.1%	48.9%	
	Divorced	80.0%	20.0%		20.0%	80.0%		20.0%	80.0%	
Nationality	Saudi	61.2%	38.8%	0.170	24.2%	75.8%	0.091	51.7%	48.3%	0.607
	Non-Saudi	100.0%	0.0%		66.7%	33.3%		66.7%	33.3%	
Smoker	Yes	58.5%	41.5%	0.479	23.1%	76.9%	0.677	52.3%	47.7%	0.940
	No	63.8%	36.2%		25.9%	74.1%		51.7%	48.3%	

*Chi-square test was used.

Table (7): Burnout levels in different domains in association with work-related factors (N=181)

Parameter		Burnout level		P-value	Depersonalization level		P-value	Personal achievement		P-value
		Low burnout	High burnout		Low burnout	High burnout		Low burnout	High burnout	
Specialty	General Surgery	55.2%	44.8%	0.020	17.2%	82.8%	0.063	44.8%	55.2%	0.302
	Obstetrics/Gynecology	65.4%	34.6%		7.7%	92.3%		57.7%	42.3%	
	Internal Medicine	63.4%	36.6%		34.1%	65.9%		61.0%	39.0%	
	Oncology	57.1%	42.9%		14.3%	85.7%		28.6%	71.4%	
	Neurology	28.6%	71.4%		14.3%	85.7%		57.1%	42.9%	
	Pediatrics	87.0%	13.0%		30.4%	69.6%		52.2%	47.8%	
	ICU	71.4%	28.6%		21.4%	78.6%		42.9%	57.1%	
	Otolaryngology	80.0%	20.0%		60.0%	40.0%		80.0%	20.0%	
	Emergency Medicine	37.5%	62.5%		25.0%	75.0%		37.5%	62.5%	
Hospital	King Abdullah Medical City	65.4%	34.6%	0.140	34.6%	65.4%	0.105	55.8%	44.2%	0.073
	Maternity and children's hospital	81.8%	18.2%		22.7%	77.3%		59.1%	40.9%	
	Al Noor Specialist Hospital	57.5%	42.5%		30.0%	70.0%		55.0%	45.0%	
	King Faisal Hospital	42.1%	57.9%		26.3%	73.7%		42.1%	57.9%	
	Hera General Hospital	65.5%	34.5%		13.8%	86.2%		62.1%	37.9%	
	Security forces Hospital	52.6%	47.4%		5.3%	94.7%		21.1%	78.9%	
Residency level	R1	61.4%	38.6%	0.516	36.8%	63.2%	0.318	57.9%	42.1%	0.049
	R2	66.0%	34.0%		21.3%	78.7%		36.2%	63.8%	
	R3	55.8%	44.2%		20.9%	79.1%		48.8%	51.2%	
	R4	72.0%	28.0%		16.0%	84.0%		64.0%	36.0%	
	R5	44.4%	55.6%		11.1%	88.9%		77.8%	22.2%	
On-call duties	Yes	64.0%	36.0%	0.099	24.2%	75.8%	0.573	53.4%	46.6%	0.257
	No	45.0%	55.0%		30.0%	70.0%		40.0%	60.0%	

*Chi-square test was used.

IX. DISCUSSION:

This study was conducted on 181 residents in Makkah from different specialties using MBI (Maslach burnout- Inventory) to assess the prevalence of Burnout among them. We found high-level burnout levels in 38.1%, 75.1%, and 48.1% in terms of burnout, depersonalization, and low personal achievements respectively with 26% suffering from high-level burnout in all domains. These results are comparably high especially in terms of depersonalization among previous studies on the subject.

In a cross-sectional study conducted on medical and surgical residents at King Abdulaziz Medical City in Riyadh 12.50% appeared with high emotional exhaustion, 51% with high depersonalization, and 31.50% showed low personal achievements. (32) A Meta-analysis included 22,778 individual participants found aggregate prevalence of burnout to be 51%. (30)

According to our results, no significant association was found between gender and any dimension of the burnout survey. This has been largely under dispute in literature with some studies leaning towards more prevalence of burnout and depersonalization among females while others finding absolutely no association between the two. (23,24,25)

Also in our study, no significant association was found between marital status and prevalence of any dimension of burnout. This comes in terms with results found by *Baharoon et al* (26) and *Dyrbye et al*. (27)

On the other hand, in a study conducted by *Jamjoom et al*. (28), it was found that partnered residents; either married or engaged, suffered from higher rates of burnout and depersonalization, but no difference was found in terms of personal achievements score. Similarly, in a study conducted by *Aldrees et al*. (29) being a single female resident was associated with higher rates of burnout.

We found a significant association between burnout level and specialty (P-Value = 0.020), with the highest recordings lying among Neurology and Emergency Medicine (71.4%, 62.5% respectively). This comes in terms with findings of *Martini et al*. who saw a high prevalence of burnout among Neurology residents (63%), however, they did not include the specialty of emergency medicine in their survey. In their results, we also find a high prevalence of burnout among Obstetrics/gynecology residents (75%) in comparison to only 34.6% in our study. Internal medicine also scored a high

prevalence (75%) in comparison to only 36.6% in our study; this variation might be attributed to the larger sample size *in Martini et al*.

A systematic review was conducted involving 26 studies (4,664 residents) classified specialties according to burnout prevalence into three categories; neurology was considered in the low-burnout prevalence group with a percentage of 23.5%. The highest in prevalence, however, were found to include general surgery, anesthesiology, obstetrics and gynecology, and orthopedics with a prevalence of 42.5%. But it is important to note that no significant association was found in this study between specialty and burnout prevalence. (22)

In a study conducted to measure pediatric residents' burnout in a tertiary academic center in Saudi Arabia, 70% of residents were found to be suffering from severe burnout, in comparison to only 13.0% suffering from high burnout, and 69.6% from the high level of depersonalization in our study.

Our findings showed no significant association between on-call duties and any dimension of the burnout survey, which is supported by previous findings by *Kamal Hameed et al*. in a study conducted on 181 residents in Saudi Arabia. The former study found no association between duty hours (including on-call) and the prevalence of burnout. (19) However, it was found in another pre-post assessment study conducted by *Martini et al*. that decreasing the number of working hours was associated with lower burnout levels among residents. (20) This variation in results might be explained by lack of follow-up in our study and in *Kamal Hameed et al*. and hence we encourage further follow-up studies to better assess this point.

It might also be crucial here to mention another pre-post assessment of burnout prevalence among surgery residents after reduction of working hours from 100 to 80 hours that showed no significant association between the reduction and prevalence of burnout. (21) This suggests the presence of other factors governing the relationship which may include the number of the sample and the specialty.

X. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

Our study supports previous findings in the prevalence of burnout syndrome among medical residents. Specialty was significantly associated with high-level burnout, most commonly among neurology residents. These findings highly recommend serious strategies to be implemented to

lessen the burden among residents.

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